

**SOME SUMMATION AND TRANSFORMATION FORMULAS
FROM INVERSION TECHNIQUES**

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Abstract

With the help of Gould–Hsu inversions, we find a generalization of Hagen and Rothe’s identity and give a new proof for some generalizations of Simons’ identity and Bruckman’s identity. Furthermore, we derive several Bruckman-type identities via the derivative operator.

1. Introduction

For any complex number x and nonnegative integer n , define the shifted-factorial to be

$$(x)_n = \Gamma(x+n)/\Gamma(x),$$

where $\Gamma(x)$ is the well-known Gamma function. There are a lot of combinatorial identities in the literature. Thereinto, Hagen and Rothe’s identity (cf. [4]) reads

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{a+\lambda k}{k} \frac{c-\lambda n}{c-\lambda k} \binom{c-\lambda k}{n-k} = \binom{a+c}{n}, \quad (1.1)$$

where $c - \lambda k \neq 0$. Replacing k by $n - k$ in Equation (1.1), we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{a+\lambda n - \lambda k}{n-k} \frac{c-\lambda n}{c-\lambda n + \lambda k} \binom{c-\lambda n + \lambda k}{k} = \binom{a+c}{n}.$$

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Replacing a and c by $c - \lambda n$ and $a + \lambda n$, respectively, in the last equation, we obtain

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{a}{a + \lambda k} \binom{a + \lambda k}{k} \binom{c - \lambda k}{n - k} = \binom{a + c}{n}, \tag{1.2}$$

where $a + \lambda k \neq 0$. The linear combination of Equation (1.1) and Equation (1.2) produces

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{a}{a + \lambda k} \binom{a + \lambda k}{k} \frac{c - \lambda n}{c - \lambda k} \binom{c - \lambda k}{n - k} = \frac{a + c - \lambda n}{a + c} \binom{a + c}{n},$$

where $a + \lambda k \neq 0$ and $c - \lambda k \neq 0$.

Following Andrews, Askey, and Roy [1], define the hypergeometric series by

$${}_{1+r}F_s \left[\begin{matrix} a_0, & a_1, & \dots, & a_r \\ b_1, & \dots, & b_s \end{matrix} ; z \right] = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_0)_k (a_1)_k \cdots (a_r)_k}{(1)_k (b_1)_k \cdots (b_s)_k} z^k,$$

where $\{a_i\}_{i \geq 0}$ and $\{b_j\}_{j \geq 1}$ are complex parameters such that no zero factors appear in the denominators of the summand on the right-hand side. In this paper, we shall establish the following generalization of Equation (1.1).

Theorem 1. *Let a, b, c, d, λ be complex numbers subject to $\min\{\Re(1 + a - b), \Re(\lambda - 1)\} > 0$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(-n)_k}{k!} \frac{\Gamma(1 + a + \lambda k) \Gamma(n - b - c + \lambda k - k)}{\Gamma(1 + a - b + \lambda k - k) \Gamma(1 - c + \lambda k)} {}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} -a - c, b, d + k \\ 1 - c + \lambda k, d \end{matrix} ; 1 \right] \\ &= \frac{(-a - c)_n (d - b)_n}{(-b - c + \lambda n) (d)_n}. \end{aligned}$$

When $b = 0$, Theorem 1 reduces to Equation (1.1) exactly. When $n = 0$, Theorem 1 becomes Gauss' summation formula:

$${}_2F_1 \left[\begin{matrix} a, b \\ c \end{matrix} ; 1 \right] = \frac{\Gamma(c) \Gamma(c - a - b)}{\Gamma(c - a) \Gamma(c - b)},$$

where $\Re(c - a - b) > 0$.

In 2001, Simons [16] proved a curious identity:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n+k} \binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} (x+1)^k = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} x^k. \tag{1.3}$$

Chapman [2] gave an interesting combinatorial proof of it. Prodinger [15] displayed another attractive proof of this identity via Cauchy's integral formula. We refer the reader to [17, 18] for two other proofs of Equation (1.3). Some related conclusions can be seen in the paper [12]. Hirschhorn [7] pointed out that Simons' identity can be deduced by specifying the parameters in Pfaff's transformation formula (cf. [1, P. 79]), which can be stated as the following theorem.

Theorem 2. *Let b, c, x be complex numbers. Then*

$${}_2F_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -n, b \\ c \end{matrix} ; x \right] = \frac{(c-b)_n}{(c)_n} {}_2F_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -n, b \\ 1+b-c-n \end{matrix} ; 1-x \right].$$

By means of Cauchy’s integral formula, Munarini [13] discovered the nice generalization of Equation (1.3):

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{\alpha}{n-k} \binom{\beta+k}{k} x^k y^{n-k} = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{\beta-\alpha+n}{n-k} \binom{\beta+k}{k} (-1)^{n-k} (x+y)^k y^{n-k}.$$

Here we point out that this result is an equivalent form of Theorem 2.

In a letter to Henry Gould on 15 April 2008, Paul Bruckman posed the following problem:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \frac{k}{(1-2k)(k+r)} = \frac{1+2n}{1+2r}, \tag{1.4}$$

where r is a positive integer with $1 \leq r \leq n$. Through Zeilberger’s Algorithm (cf. [14, Chapter 6]), Gould [5] established an interesting generalization of Bruckman’s identity (1.4), which can be expressed the following theorem.

Theorem 3. *Let x be a complex number. Then*

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \frac{k}{(1-2k)(k+x)} = \frac{1+2n}{1+2x} - \frac{1}{1+2x} \frac{(1-x)_n}{(1+x)_n}. \tag{1.5}$$

It should be mentioned that Xu and Cen [18] also proved Theorem 3 in terms of the contour integral method.

For a differentiable function $f(x)$, define the derivative operator \mathcal{D}_x as

$$\mathcal{D}_x f(x) = \frac{d}{dx} f(x).$$

For any complex number x and positive integer ℓ , define the generalized harmonic numbers of ℓ -order to be

$$H_0^{(\ell)}(x) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad H_n^{(\ell)}(x) = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{(x+k)^\ell} \quad \text{when} \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}^+.$$

Setting $\ell = 1$ in $H_0^{(\ell)}(x)$ and $H_n^{(\ell)}(x)$, we get generalized harmonic numbers

$$H_0(x) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad H_n(x) = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{x+k}.$$

When $x = 0$, they reduce to classical harmonic numbers

$$H_0 = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad H_n = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k}.$$

Applying the derivative operator \mathcal{D}_x to both sides of Equation (1.5), we arrive at the following result.

Theorem 4. *Let x be a complex number. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \frac{k}{(1-2k)(k+x)^2} \\ &= \frac{2+4n}{(1+2x)^2} - \frac{1}{(1+2x)} \frac{(1-x)_n}{(1+x)_n} \left\{ \frac{2}{1+2x} + H_n(x) + H_n(-x) \right\}. \end{aligned} \tag{1.6}$$

Fixing $x = r$ in Theorem 4 and utilizing the relation

$$\begin{aligned} (1-x)_n H_n(-x) &= (1-x)_{r-1} (r-x) (1+r-x)_{n-r} \\ &\quad \times \left\{ H_{r-1}(-x) + \frac{1}{r-x} + H_{n-r}(r-x) \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

we can derive the following formula.

Corollary 5. *Let r be a positive integer with $1 \leq r \leq n$. Then*

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \frac{k}{(1-2k)(k+r)^2} = \frac{2+4n}{(1+2r)^2} + \frac{(-1)^r}{(1+2r)} \frac{(1)_{r-1} (1)_{n-r}}{(1+r)_n}.$$

Applying the derivative operator \mathcal{D}_x to both sides of Equation (1.6), we are led to the following conclusion.

Theorem 6. *Let x be a complex number. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \frac{k}{(1-2k)(k+x)^3} \\ &= \frac{4+8n}{(1+2x)^3} - \frac{1}{(2+4x)} \frac{(1-x)_n}{(1+x)_n} \left\{ \frac{8}{(1+2x)^2} + \Omega_n(x) \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_n(x) &= \left[\frac{4}{1+2x} + H_n(x) + H_n(-x) \right] [H_n(x) + H_n(-x)] \\ &\quad + [H_n^{(2)}(x) - H_n^{(2)}(-x)]. \end{aligned}$$

Choosing $x = r$ in Theorem 6, we can deduce the following formula.

Corollary 7. *Let r be a positive integer with $1 \leq r \leq n$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \frac{k}{(1-2k)(k+r)^3} \\ &= \frac{4+8n}{(1+2r)^3} + \frac{(-1)^r}{(1+2r)} \frac{(1)_{r-1}(1)_{n-r}}{(1+r)_n} \left\{ H_{n+r} + H_{n-r} - 2H_r + \frac{1+4r}{r(1+2r)} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

For a complex variable x and two complex sequences $\{a_k, b_k\}_{k \geq 0}$, define a polynomial sequence by

$$\phi(x; 0) \equiv 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \phi(x; n) = \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} (a_i + x b_i) \quad \text{when} \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}^+.$$

Then a pair of inverse series relations due to Gould and Hsu [6] can be written as

$$f(n) = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} \phi(k; n) g(k), \tag{1.7}$$

$$g(n) = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} \frac{a_k + k b_k}{\phi(n; k+1)} f(k). \tag{1.8}$$

Inversion techniques are very useful for dealing with combinatorial identities. Some nice results can be seen in the papers [3, 8–11].

Inspired by the works just mentioned, we shall prove Theorems 1-3 by using Gould–Hsu inversions (1.7) and (1.8). The corresponding details will be provided in Sections 2-4, respectively.

2. Proof of Theorem 1

In order to prove Theorem 1, we require the following transformation formula (cf. [1, P. 142]):

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, b, c \\ d, e \end{matrix} ; 1 \right] = \frac{\Gamma(e)\Gamma(d+e-a-b-c)}{\Gamma(e-a)\Gamma(d+e-b-c)} {}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, d-b, d-c \\ d, d+e-b-c \end{matrix} ; 1 \right]. \tag{2.1}$$

Proof of Theorem 1. Performing the replacements $a \rightarrow -n, b \rightarrow -a - c, c \rightarrow d - b, d \rightarrow 1 - b - c + \lambda n - n, e \rightarrow d$ in Equation (2.1), we obtain

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} \frac{-b-c+\lambda k}{(-b-c+\lambda n-n)_{k+1}} \frac{(-a-c)_k (d-b)_k}{(-b-c+\lambda k)(d)_k}$$

$$= \frac{(1+a+\lambda n-n)_n}{(-b-c+\lambda n-n)(d)_n} {}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} -n, 1+a-b+\lambda n-n, 1-c-d+\lambda n-n \\ 1-b-c+\lambda n-n, 1+a+\lambda n-n \end{matrix} ; 1 \right].$$

It satisfies Equation (1.8) and Equation (1.7) brings out the dual relation:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} (-b-c+\lambda k-k)_n \frac{(1+a+\lambda k-k)_k}{(-b-c+\lambda k-k)(d)_k}$$

$$\times {}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 1+a-b+\lambda k-k, 1-c-d+\lambda k-k \\ 1-b-c+\lambda k-k, 1+a+\lambda k-k \end{matrix} ; 1 \right]$$

$$= \frac{(-a-c)_n (d-b)_n}{(-b-c+\lambda n)(d)_n}. \tag{2.2}$$

The iteration of Equation (2.1) results in the transformation formula (cf. [1, P. 143]):

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, b, c \\ d, e \end{matrix} ; 1 \right] = \frac{\Gamma(d)\Gamma(e)\Gamma(d+e-a-b-c)}{\Gamma(a)\Gamma(d+e-a-b)\Gamma(d+e-a-c)}$$

$$\times {}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} d-a, e-a, d+e-a-b-c \\ d+e-a-b, d+e-a-c \end{matrix} ; 1 \right]. \tag{2.3}$$

Employing the replacements $a \rightarrow 1+a-b+\lambda k-k$, $b \rightarrow -k$, $c \rightarrow 1-c-d+\lambda k-k$, $d \rightarrow 1-b-c+\lambda k-k$, $e \rightarrow 1+a+\lambda k-k$ in Equation (2.3), we have

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 1+a-b+\lambda k-k, 1-c-d+\lambda k-k \\ 1-b-c+\lambda k-k, 1+a+\lambda k-k \end{matrix} ; 1 \right]$$

$$= \frac{\Gamma(1-b-c+\lambda k-k)\Gamma(1+a+\lambda k-k)\Gamma(d+k)}{\Gamma(1+a-b+\lambda k-k)\Gamma(1-c+\lambda k)\Gamma(d)}$$

$$\times {}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} -a-c, b, d+k \\ 1-c+\lambda k, d \end{matrix} ; 1 \right]. \tag{2.4}$$

Substituting Equation (2.4) into Equation (2.2), we get Theorem 1 after some simplifications. □

3. Proof of Theorem 2

For the sake of proving Theorem 2, we draw support from the binomial theorem and Chu–Vandermonde convolution (cf. [1, P. 67]):

$${}_1F_0 \left[\begin{matrix} -n \\ - \end{matrix} ; x \right] = (1-x)^n, \tag{3.1}$$

$${}_2F_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -n, b \\ c \end{matrix} ; 1 \right] = \frac{(c-b)_n}{(c)_n}. \tag{3.2}$$

Proof of Theorem 2. According to Equations (3.1) and (3.2), it is routine to verify that

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(-n)_i (b)_i}{i! (1+c-b-n)_i} (-x)^i \sum_{k=0}^{n-i} \frac{(-n+i)_k (c+i)_k}{k! (1+c-b-n+i)_k} = \frac{(b)_n}{(b-c)_n} (1-x)^n.$$

Shifting the summation index $k \rightarrow k-i$ and then interchanging the summation order in the last equation, we arrive at

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} (b-c-k)_n \frac{(c)_k}{(1+c-b)_k} \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{(-k)_i (b)_i}{i! (c)_i} x^i = (b)_n (1-x)^n.$$

It suits to Equation (1.7), and Equation (1.8) gives the dual relation

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} \frac{b-c}{(b-c-n)_{k+1}} (b)_k (1-x)^k = \frac{(c)_n}{(1+c-b)_n} \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(-n)_i (b)_i}{i! (c)_i} x^i.$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 2. □

4. Proof of Theorem 3

For the purpose of proving Theorem 3, we need the following lemma.

Lemma 8. *Let n be a nonnegative integer and let x be a complex number. Then*

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(-n)_k}{(2+n)_k} (1+2k)^2 = \frac{1+n}{1-2n}, \tag{4.1}$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(-n)_k (1-x)_k}{(2+n)_k (1+x)_k} (1+2k) = \frac{x(1+n)}{x+n}. \tag{4.2}$$

Proof. It is not difficult to show that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(-n)_k (b)_k}{k! (2+n)_k} (1+2k)^2 \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(-n)_k (b)_k}{k! (2+n)_k} + 4 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-n)_k (b)_k}{k! (2+n)_k} k + 4 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-n)_k (b)_k}{k! (2+n)_k} k^2 \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(-n)_k (b)_k}{k! (2+n)_k} - \frac{8bn}{2+n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{(1-n)_k (1+b)_k}{k! (3+n)_k} \\ &\quad - \frac{4b(1+b)n(1-n)}{(2+n)(3+n)} \sum_{k=0}^{n-2} \frac{(2-n)_k (2+b)_k}{k! (4+n)_k}. \end{aligned}$$

Taking $b = 1$ in the last equation and then evaluating the three series on the right-hand side by Equation (3.2), we obtain Equation (4.1).

Setting $a = 1, b = 1, c = 1 - x$ in Dougall’s summation formula for ${}_5F_4$ series (cf. [1, P. 71]):

$${}_5F_4 \left[\begin{matrix} a, 1 + \frac{a}{2}, b, c, -n \\ \frac{a}{2}, 1 + a - b, 1 + a - c, 1 + a + n \end{matrix} ; 1 \right] = \frac{(1+a)_n (1+a-b-c)_n}{(1+a-b)_n (1+a-c)_n},$$

we get Equation (4.2). □

Now we prove Theorem 3.

Proof of Theorem 3. In accordance with Lemma 8, it is easy to see that

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} \frac{1+2k}{(1+n)_{k+1}} k! \left\{ \frac{1+2k}{1+2x} - \frac{1}{1+2x} \frac{(1-x)_k}{(1+x)_k} \right\} = \frac{n}{(1-2n)(n+x)}.$$

The last equation fits into Equation(1.8), and Equation (1.7) produces the dual relation

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k} (1+k)_n \frac{k}{(1-2k)(k+x)} = n! \left\{ \frac{1+2n}{1+2x} - \frac{1}{1+2x} \frac{(1-x)_n}{(1+x)_n} \right\}.$$

This completes the proof. □

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